

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE FORMATION OF MORAL CHARACTERS THROUGH COMMUNICATION IN PRIMARY SCHOOL AGE

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the interpretation of moral qualities by eastern thinkers in the formation of communication skills at the junior school age and the features of the formation of moral qualities in elementary school students through communication are presented.

ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ НРАВСТВЕННЫХ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИК ЧЕРЕЗ ОБЩЕНИЕ В МЛАДШЕМ ШКОЛЬНОМ ВОЗРАСТЕ

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ABSTRACT

Помогает в просмотре трех школьных статей в юном возрасте посредством интерпретации моральных качеств мыслителей-комментаторов и передачи моральных качеств учащимся класса.

KICHIK MAKTAB YOSHIDA MULOQOT ORQALI AXLOQIY SIFATLARNI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI

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Muloqot, axloqiy sifat, sharq mutaffakkirlari, muloqot o'rgatish usullari, til, nutq.

ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqolada kichik maktab yoshida muloqot ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda axloqiy sifatlarning sharq mutaffakkirlari tomonidan talqini va boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida axloqiy sifatlari muloqot orqali shakllantirish xususiyatlari keltirib o'tilgan

The urgency of the problem: A concept that indicates that the constant habit of moral views that encourage people to do good and prevent them from evil has become a practical activity. It embodies the examples of human manners and forms the core of spirituality. It is known that the culture, philosophy, and worldview of the peoples of the East have been glorifying the moral qualities of a person since ancient times. In this sense, Eastern social thought and literature can be called an encyclopedia of moral qualities. Eastern thinkers such as Imam Bukhari, Imam Tirmizi, Muhammad Musa Khorezmi, Rudaki, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Hafiz Shirozi, Fuzuli, Khusrav Dehlavi, Abdurrahman Jami, Alisher Nawai, thinkers such as moral qualities in their scientific and creative activities. of course, the importance of communication in the formation of moral qualities is incomparable, and Vygotsky believed that language develops from social interactions for the purpose of communication. He considered language to be the best tool for people, a way to communicate with the outside world. According to Vygotsky, language plays two important roles in cognitive development:

1. It is the main means by which adults convey information to children.
2. Language itself becomes a very powerful tool of intellectual adaptation.

One of the ways to teach communication is formation in the form of exercises. The educator teaches the child to communicate by conducting various activities in kindergarten. First, basic manners, how to talk to adults, how to say hello, how to express gratitude are included. During school age and later, a person is taught to communicate by organizing social and psychological training. It is necessary for the person to respond positively to these methods, to take active action, because without communication, the person cannot fully develop as a subject of activity and as an individual. School has long been preparing children for themselves both academically and morally. life in a society that has been viewed as an institution to be. It is a social organization with many norms and values imparted by teachers. Besides parents, teachers are the people who have the greatest influence on children's development, including academic achievement, social behavior, values and personality. requires undertaking.

The purpose of the study: In the process of mastering moral norms and rules of behavior, the foundation of moral behavior is laid in the period of junior school age, moral norms and rules of behavior are mastered. The social orientation of the person begins to take shape. The moral consciousness of students of junior school age undergoes significant changes

during the period from the 1st to the 4th grade. By the last stages of this age, moral knowledge, ideas and opinions are significantly enriched, they become more aware, they have different concepts, they generalize. The moral judgments of 1st and 2nd graders are based on the experience of their behavior and concrete instructions and explanations of teachers and parents. 3rd- 4th grade students try to analyze other people's experiences based on their own behavior experience and adults' instructions in their moral judgments. 7-8-year-old children do not wait directly for the instructions of adults, including the teacher, but carry out many positive moral actions on their own initiative. Analyzing the character traits and behaviors that appear in children of small school age, it is not always the case that relationships are stable and stable forms of behavior. In children of junior school age, the character begins to form seriously.

Material and methods: The character and behavior of children of junior school age may differ in their instability and contradictions. In this regard, sometimes transient mental states in them can be mistakenly added to their character. In Ibn Sina's opinion, he emphasizes that it is important for communication to be a culture of people influencing each other and entering into a relationship in the social process. Ibn Sina said that his moral maturity is important for a person's maturation, he was able to see the good qualities of a person by deeply illuminating the issues of moral education on a philosophical-pedagogical basis.

Research results: According to Ibn Sina, one of the best qualities of a person is to realize his bad moral qualities and try to get rid of them. It is to observe the culture of communication when talking with others. Also, his moral views are consistent with his thoughts on beauty and elegance. Confirming the above points, communication culture is considered one of the moral qualities of a person. Because in the process of communication, from one point of view, through the external appearance of a person, his inner world is also revealed. Depending on the culture of the person's behavior, his inner world is also manifested. In the views of Eastern thinkers on education, human dignity, knowledge, respect for wise people, hospitality, kindness, courage and bravery, humility are promoted as human qualities in general. Above, while studying the views of our thinkers on communication etiquette, we once again realized that communication etiquette is of great importance in determining a person's life and his place in society. That's why education of communication etiquette of students is considered as one of the important aspects of education, formation of communication etiquette in students has an important place in finding its place in the community and society.

In conclusion: that the role of moral qualities in the formation of communication skills in students of junior school age is incomparable. It is important to morally influence young school-age students who have difficulties in implementation, to bring up the process of communication through thinking, and for the child, school is an important place to enter the communication process more widely, if the child actively participates in the communication process. communication is important in building skills.

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